

**METHOD OF APPLICATION FOR RESTORATION OF THE MAIN
ARTERIAL BLOOD FLOW OF THE LOWER EXTREMITIES
IN DIABETIC FOOT**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7246806>

Purpose: To develop a new way to restore the main blood flow of the lower extremities in chronic arterial insufficiency, providing adequate blood flow in case of occlusion and stenosis of the tibial and foot arteries.

MATERIAL AND METHODS: The results of treatment of 36 patients who underwent antegrade recanalization of the tibial and foot arteries through popliteal access were analyzed. From January to March 2022, 36 endovascular interventions on the tibial and foot arteries were performed. The technical success was 99%. All patients (100%) suffered from diabetes mellitus. The observation period was 3 months. Patients underwent ultrasound duplex scanning with measurement of ABI every 1 month.

RESULTS: Antegrade recanalization of the tibial and foot arteries was performed in 36 patients (24 men and 12 women, mean age 68 years). All patients had diabetic foot. The antegrade popliteal approach was successful in 100% (n-36) of patients (posterior tibial = 28, anterior tibial = 25). All patients (100%) underwent balloon angioplasty. Revascularization failed in 1 patient (2.7%). There were no access-related complications of early and late postoperative access. The average increase in ABI was 0.4. There were no deaths or amputations during the hospital period. In the long-term period, all 36 patients were followed up; in all of them, the access artery was passable on the basis of MSCT angiography of the lower extremities.

CONCLUSIONS: The immediate results of antegrade access from the popliteal arteries show that it is safe and effective, without complications and mortality. This method expands the possibilities of endovascular interventions after unsuccessful antegrade revascularizations from the common femoral artery.